

EUROPEAN POLICY BRIEF

Action for Rural Women's Empowerment (ARUWE) is one of the partners implementing the Science Transformation in Europe through Citizens involvement in Health, conservation and Energy Research (STEPCHANGE). The project focuses on establishing the evidence of, and bolster Off-grid Renewable Energy (RE) in agricultural production in rural Uganda, with particular focus on solar, charcoal briquettes and biogas renewable energy technologies. The main objective of the study is to provide evidence of the economic, environmental and societal potential of adopting off-grid renewable energy in agricultural production in rural Uganda. The study pursued four specific objectives, namely: a) Identify the impact achieved by ongoing projects in Kyankwanzi, Kiboga and Luwero districts where agricultural cooperatives have been trained and mobilized to use renewable energy technologies to promote agricultural productivity; b) Identify the impact achieved due to adoption of renewable energy technologies in agriculture production in other districts in Uganda; c) Provide evidence on the potential of up-scaling of the technology transfer experiences to the whole region and provides an estimate of the up-scaling potential at national level; and d) Analyze the current policy and institutional framework on the use of RE technologies in agricultural production in Uganda.

Based on the collected results, a policy brief was presented to the decision makers in a multi- stakeholders and fact-based dialogue conducted on the potential upscaling at regional and National levels of the process of technology transfer and adoption. Advised by the stakeholder, three separate policy briefs were prepared for systematic implementation advocacy and monitoring

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Off-grid Renewable Energy in Agriculture

Promoting the Adoption of Solar Technology in Uganda for Increased Agricultural Productivity, Profitability, and Sustainability

This policy brief reviews policy and practice in the use of solar technology in agriculture with a particular focus on their impact on rural farming communities in Uganda. An integrated set of policy recommendations is proposed to address the specific challenges and barriers including financing, regulations, multi-stakeholder collaboration, private sector investment, and capacity building. These actions are required to support the widespread adoption of solar energy which aims to: (i) enhance the performance of Uganda's agricultural sector, (ii) result in meeting food and nutrition security targets, and (iii) as well as achieve the country's overall targets for renewable energy. The adoption of solar technology in agricultural production aligns seamlessly with the African food systems transformation agenda, a critical initiative aimed at addressing the unique challenges facing Africa's agriculture and food security.

Solar system at Tumwebaze fruit farm that supports fishing and lighting. Photo credit: ARUWE

Economic policymakers in developing nations continue to place a strong priority on ensuring food security since it is directly related to social stability in these areas, where poverty can reach extremely high levels. FAO reports that nearly 720 million people globally were undernourished in 2020, and more than 3 billion people could not afford a healthy diet. Most of these people live in developing countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa. In Uganda, food insecurity persists, and as such achievement of Goal 2 of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) remains a priority. By the end of 2020, 69.2% (30.6 million) Ugandans were food insecure among which 21.7% (9.6 million) were severely food insecure (FAO et al., 2021).

One promising approach for sub-Saharan African nations to reverse these troubling trends is having access to energy in agriculture. Energy is required at every stage of the agricultural value chains, including crop production, fisheries, livestock, and forestry; post-harvest processing, food storage, transport, and distribution; and food preparation. However, access to affordable and reliable energy remains a challenge. The International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA) estimates that 600 million people globally lack access to electricity, most of them in sub-Saharan Africa (IEA, 2022). A high percentage of Uganda's energy consumption comes from renewable sources, but mainly from traditional firewood and charcoal. The high reliance on biomass as a fuel brings added burdens to livelihoods including harm to public health, diminished opportunities, particularly for women and girls who are responsible for collecting biomass, environmental degradation, and a contribution to climate change. In 2020, modern renewables made up only 22% of total energy use. To prevent additional deforestation, emissions, and health hazards, a swift shift to renewable energy is therefore required.

The Untapped Potential of Solar Energy

Uganda recognizes and is committed to deploying renewable energy technologies as one of the strategies for achieving international targets. Several reforms are already in place, including the launch of the Renewable Energy Policy 2007. Uganda also opted in the Sustainable Energy for All (SEforALL) initiative and prepared a rapid assessment followed by an action agenda, which was formally adopted by the government. The agenda sets the goal of achieving more than 90% of renewable energy production by 2030. Renewables are the backbone of the energy transition and a viable climate solution.

A shift to solar energy is a testament to the global trend towards renewable energy and a strategic move to diversify the energy mix and boost agricultural production and economic growth. Oting et al. (2018) project that solar energy use in Uganda will surpass hydropower by 2050, indicating its potential. The 2019/2020 national household survey indicates that solar connections the country increased to 38% from 18% in 2017 compared to a dip in hydro and grid connections which decreased from 22% to 19% during the same period (UBOS, 2021). For agricultural production, solar energy presents a compelling solution that can address several critical challenges facing the sector today. Its adoption in agriculture can be traced to lighting, irrigation, harvesting, preservation, and processing among others. Solar-powered irrigation systems are pivotal tools that can empower farmers to optimize their crop production, even in regions with unreliable access to conventional energy sources. By extending the growing seasons and reducing water scarcity constraints, solar technology contributes directly to increased crop yields, enhanced food security, and enhanced overall economic resilience. The decentralised nature of solar energy systems allows farmers to generate their own energy on-site, reducing dependence on centralised grids and minimizing energy transmission losses. This aspect is particularly valuable in rural and remote agricultural areas where grid infrastructure is lacking or unreliable.

The adoption of solar technology in agricultural production aligns seamlessly with the African food systems transformation agenda, a critical initiative aimed at addressing the unique challenges facing Africa's agriculture and food security. In the context of this transformative agenda, solar technology serves as a potent catalyst for change by enhancing agricultural sustainability, resilience, and efficiency across the continent.

Using citizen science¹ approach, ARUWE undertook a study to gather evidence of economic, environmental, and societal impacts of adopting solar technology in the agricultural production in rural Uganda and exploring the potential for scaling up the technology at the national level. Data were collected from seven rural districts in Uganda: Kiboga, Kyankwanzi, Luwero, Mityana and Nakaseke districts in Central Uganda; Kamuli district in Eastern Uganda; and Nebbi district in Northwest Uganda, with 1,068 gathered responses through individual interviews and 48 in six focus group discussions. At the national level, 20 key informant interviews were conducted targeting government ministries and departments, the private sector, and non-government organisations involved in the promotion of solar technology. Case stories of the successful use of solar technology in agriculture were also captured.

Survey results showed that solar technology has the highest current adoption (77% of respondents) and the highest potential for scale-up. The main benefits for solar adoption mentioned by farmers were energy efficiency, health and safety concerns, low maintenance costs, benefits from use, and incentives to adopt (Figure 1). Farmers indicated that they used solar energy for brooding and lighting their poultry farms, irrigation, and drying. They mentioned associated benefits include time savings, environmental impact, reduced cost of production, and improved productivity. The main barriers to the adoption of solar technology were the high initial costs which are not affordable for most smallholder farmers, and a general lack of awareness about the technology. Conversely, with about 37% (up to 60% in Kyankwanzi) indicating that they were incentivised to adopt solar through receiving initial funding for the installations, which implies, despite the minimal operational and maintenance costs, that scaling-up of solar technology could be significantly hindered by high initial costs, requiring policy attention to enable affordability.

Figure 1: Reasons that attract farmers to adopt solar technology (left), and benefits realised in using solar technology (right).

Atla Farm Solar Irrigation Scheme

The Atla farm is located in Opedhere village, Acwera parish, Alala sub county, Nebbi district in Northwest Uganda. The farm received solar pump equipment estimated at UGX 30,000,000 (approx. Euro 7,200) from “Friends of Angal” in 2018 and bought the farmland near the river to ease irrigation. The irrigation system is currently used for short-term crops like onions, eggplants, kale, tomatoes, and watermelons. The use of solar irrigation has enabled all-year crop production and food availability, coupled with significant savings on buying fuel which was the case before as the farm relied on a gasoline engine pump. For instance, the farm used approximately 5 liters of petrol daily which is equivalent to UGX30,000 (approx. Euro 6). The farm has become financially self-sustaining through the continuous flow of income.

¹ Citizen science is scientific research conducted with participation from the general public.

Regarding the potential for scaling up solar irrigation, Robert, the farm owner, observed that the current challenges of unreliable and low rainfall patterns coupled with the location of Uganda within the tropics (and more so crossed by the equator), offering great potential to exploit solar pump innovations to boost agriculture production in Uganda. He proposed collaborative governmental and nongovernmental interventions around mass sensitisation and awareness creation on RE technologies and the provision of RE technology grants to foster adoption, reflecting that the costs of installation at Atla farm were evidently impeding the deployment of the solar irrigation if there would have been no external support.

Solar powered irrigation in Nkokonjeru Area cooperative, Mukono. Photo credit: ARUWE

Barriers for solar technology adoption

Despite solar energy being Uganda's most abundant and promising renewable energy source, available data indicate low solar energy installation. In 2001, the Ugandan government launched the Rural Electrification Strategy and Plan (RESP) for the use of solar technology in rural areas but achieved only 8.75% of the expected target over the 11-years period (Hansen et al., 2014). The lack of sufficient consumer financing, coupled with high interest rates for solar products, have depressed demand and made solar products unaffordable for many. Although the markets for solar household systems and off-grid lanterns have expanded, the technical services infrastructure, which includes the ability for design, manufacture, and assembly as well as installation and service provision, has not kept pace with the sharp rise in the number of sub-standard solar products available for purchase. Customers have thus had to cope with poor quality issues, improper installs, and technical issues with their gadgets.

The lack of public and policy awareness also remains a main barrier in the utilisation of solar technologies in Uganda. The most common issues associated with this are inadequate knowledge regarding the use, importance, costs and effectiveness, and socio-economic and environmental benefits that are derivable from such technologies. And the additional fears in relation to the economic feasibility of solar projects live on. There are also noted institutional barriers to the promotion of solar technology such as lack of coordination and cooperation between and within related ministries, agencies, and institutions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Technical Assistance and Training

The development of training programmes and provision of technical assistance to smallholder farmers, and other intermediaries are necessary to ensure the knowledge and skills needed to install, operate, and maintain solar systems effectively. The availability of technical expertise is a key determinant of technology scale-up. This gap has been considerably bridged by government, non-government, and private business organisations through the training of community-based resource persons to support the installation, service, and repair of RE technologies, as well as the training of technicians. The availability of such professionals helps in curbing challenges related to solar design and installation services. Further on there is a need to launch awareness campaigns and educational programmes to inform smallholder farmers about the benefits of solar technology, its cost-effectiveness, and available government support.

Strengthening Local Supply Chains

There is a need to support the development of local solar technology supply chains and maintenance services to ensure that smallholder farmers have access to quality products and reliable technical support. A list of viable companies working in solar energy was published by the Uganda Investment Authority, but most of these companies are from Europe. There is also a need to invest in local research and development to create solar solutions specifically designed for smallholder farmers' needs, including efficient irrigation systems, solar-powered cold storage, and affordable solar lanterns for lighting. Similarly, promoting the growth of local markets for solar technology by fostering partnerships between government, private sector companies, and NGOs can lead to increased availability and affordability of solar products in rural areas.

Energy Efficiency Regulations

With many market players providing and supplying solar equipment, there is a need to develop and enforce energy efficiency standards for solar equipment to ensure that smallholder farmers invest in reliable and long-lasting technology that provides value for money. The government should also consider the development of Grid Interconnection Policies, that allow smallholder farmers to sell excess energy generated by their solar systems back to the grid, providing them with additional income and incentivizing solar adoption.

Financial inclusion

Currently, solar panels are duty-free but other related components like lamps and batteries attract a 24% import duty. This tax regime and the high capital investment, makes the adoption of solar energy costly and unaffordable for many farmers. Governments can provide subsidies, grants, or tax incentives to reduce the upfront costs of purchasing and installing solar technology. These financial incentives can make solar solutions more affordable for smallholder farmers. In addition, there is a need for private and public partnerships to establish financing mechanisms that offer smallholder farmers access to low-interest loans or microfinance options tailored for solar technology investments. Formation of solar cooperatives or community-based organisations that enable smallholder farmers to pool resources and collectively invest in solar technology will make it more accessible and cost-effective.

Policy coordination

The Ministry of Energy and Mineral Development in Uganda has a full-fledged department for promoting and incorporating RE. Section 4.1.2 of the current draft National Energy Policy 2019 recognizes grid-connected solar power, solar thermal technologies, and off-grid energy access (MEMD, 2019). However, there are noted institutional barriers to the promotion of solar technology such as lack of coordination and cooperation between and within related ministries, agencies, and institutions. There is a need to ensure coordination among relevant government agencies, departments, and ministries to create a cohesive policy framework that

supports solar technology adoption among smallholder farmers. By implementing a combination of these policy interventions, governments can help smallholder farmers overcome barriers and embrace solar technology, leading to increased productivity, improved livelihoods, and a more sustainable agricultural sector.

Monitoring and Evaluation

In addition, a monitoring and evaluation system needs to be established to assess the impact of solar technology adoption on smallholder farmers' productivity, income, and quality of life. Monitoring and evaluation data is also critical for refining policies and interventions.

Summary of actions, responsibility, and impact

No.	Objective	Action	Responsibility	Expected impact
1	Expertise in solar technology	Training of community-based persons	Government, Private sector	Improved knowledge and skills for solar cell design and installation are crucial factors for scale-up.
2	Awareness of solar technology	Launch awareness campaigns and educational programmes for smallholders	Government, Private sector, NGOs, CBO	Enhanced knowledge about the benefits of solar technology is important for wide-scale adoption.
3	Functional local solar technology supply chains	Research and development to create solar solutions tailored to smallholders' needs	Government, Private sector	Enhanced access to appropriate and affordable solar solutions increases technology adoption.
4	Financial incentives for solar solutions	Provide subsidies, grants, or tax incentives to suppliers and users	Government	Reduced upfront costs of purchasing and installing solar solutions make it more affordable for smallholders.
5	Financial inclusion	Establish innovative financing mechanisms for smallholders	Government, Private sector, NGOs	Increased access to affordable financial services stimulates the adoption of solar solutions.
6	Energy efficiency regulations	Develop energy efficiency standards for solar equipment	Government	Enhanced quality enables smallholder investment in reliable and long-lasting solutions that provide value for money.
7	Policy coordination	Enhance coordination among relevant government ministries, departments, and agencies	Government	Improved coordination leads to the creation of a cohesive policy framework that supports solar technology adoption among smallholders.
8	Monitoring and Evaluation	Document the impact of solar technology on livelihoods	Government, Private sector, NGOs	Increased evidence critical for policy formulation and enhanced practice to enable wide-scale adoption of solar solutions.

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PROJECT IDENTITY

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Off-grid Renewable Energy in Agriculture

Accelerating Biogas Energy Generation Systems and Adoption in Uganda

This policy brief aims to demonstrate the potential of biogas renewable energy generation systems for agricultural production. Small-scale biogas energy generation to provide off-grid electricity is of growing interest. Unlike other forms of renewable energy, biogas technology offers numerous advantages, such as waste management which is a significant problem in Africa. The adoption of biogas energy in Uganda contributes to integration into the national energy mix, aligning with sustainability goals. It also has a great potential to empower rural women, contribute to economic development, and address environmental concerns by reducing reliance on traditional biomass.

Cover photo: Farmer feeding biogas plant with cow dung (Photo credit: ARUWE)

Access to modern energy is a significant concern for domestic and commercial activities in Africa's farming. Over 2.7 billion people in sub-Saharan Africa, rely predominantly on traditional biomass for their energy needs (Sehgal, 2018). In Uganda, both rural and urban populations heavily rely on biomass due to its accessibility and affordability, constituting 90% of the total energy consumed (Sehgal, 2018). However, there are concerns about the sustainability of biomass supplies and the environmental impacts resulting from their use, with the direct impacts being increased deforestation (McCarthy & Thatcher, 2019).

Biogas energy could mitigate the negative health and environmental effects while safeguarding energy access for disadvantaged communities, especially if local residues such as fecal matter and animal waste are utilised as feedstock. The integration of biogas technology into agriculture, popularly called ecological farming, will improve the income levels of farmers especially women, and facilitate the achievement of effective and low-cost productivity in agricultural systems. Biogas technology therefore provides a link between animal husbandry and crop farming, playing an important role in self-sustaining eco-farming and waste management which is a significant problem in Africa.

Agriculture is known to contribute significantly to global climate change; nevertheless, the transformation of animal wastes and other agricultural wastes will reduce the impact agriculture has on the environment. Recent initiatives have resulted in the development of a policy agenda on biogas promotion, enabling accelerated uptake and understanding of the technology in various African countries. National biogas programmes have been implemented in Kenya, Uganda, Ethiopia, Tanzania, Rwanda, Cameroon, Burkina Faso, and Benin. Notably, there is potential for large-scale biogas systems, as evidenced by successful models in China and India (Cheng et al., 2019). Based on factors like water availability, livestock ownership, population density, fuelwood scarcity, and climate, biogas is technically feasible for a significant number of households in Africa. For instance, 18.5 million households in 24 African countries, including 1.3 million households in Uganda, showed potential for adopting biogas (Rupf et al., 2015).

A proven growing industry in Uganda

Biogas technology, as a pro-poor renewable energy source, has been promoted in Uganda since the 1980s by the government and NGOs. The Uganda biogas market continues to grow, and currently, the production and utilisation of biogas stands at 25.8%. Biogas can be produced from simple organic raw materials such as animal dung, food wastes, agricultural residues, municipal waste materials, and human waste. Anaerobic digestion of organic wastes results in the production of biogas and a nutrient-rich digestate which can be plowed back to crop/fodder production as manure offering promising solution to enhance agricultural productivity.

Uganda possesses significant potential for biogas production and utilisation, driven by abundant biomass resources from a thriving agricultural sector and a predominantly rural economy. Uganda has the potential to produce 25.17 petajoules of biogas annually, which represents about 40% of the total primary energy consumption (62.56 PJ) in the country. This potentially aligns with the country's need for decentralised and sustainable energy sources, particularly in areas with limited access to electricity.

Efforts are underway to scale up renewable energy technologies in agricultural production in Uganda. Political and legal support is evident in policies such as the Energy Policy (2002), and the National Renewable Energy Policy (2007) which prioritize sustainable development through increased modern renewable energy use. The Agricultural Policy (2013), Vision 2040, and the third National Development Plan (NDP3) all provide a framework for renewable access to aid agricultural growth and competitiveness of the sector. Complementing this, are the Biomass Energy Strategy and the Global Energy Transfer Feed in Tariff (GET FIT) programme, while the Biofuels Act 2018, seeks to blend petroleum with up to 20% biofuels and boost power generation from municipal waste, aligning with broader goals for sustainable bioenergy development.

Institutional frameworks are in place for the promotion of biogas technology. The Ministry of Energy and Mineral Development (MEMD) oversees these initiatives, supported by departments advocating for climate-friendly practices. Besides, every district has a department of environment charged with the promotion of RE technologies as part of environment conservation. It is also important to note that the government has licensed local and international NGOs and business enterprises to supplement government initiatives in promoting RE technologies, thus fostering opportunities to scale up the adoption of RE technologies.

Leveraging existing biogas programmes in the country

The Ugandan government created the Uganda Domestic Biogas Programme in 2008, aimed at encouraging the rural and semi-urban populace to adopt the technology and benefit from using clean energy in lighting, cooking, and bio-slurry in agriculture to improve yields. In the same vein, MEMD promoted the installation of biogas plants in the central, western, and eastern regions (Mukisa et al., 2022). Since then, many initiatives by the government, NGOs (e.g., Heifer Project International, Adventist Relief Agencies, Africa 2000 Network, among others), private individuals, and development partners have continued to promote it.

The existence of development partners and NGOs that lobby, advocate, and support biogas promotion and extension of such technologies is recognised by several scholars. These include development partners and international and local organisations. Such institutions not only support farmers but also government departments and agencies.

CASE STUDY

Farmer characteristics

Using Citizens Science² ARUWE undertook a study in the districts of Kiboga, Kyankwanzi and Luwero to understand predominant farming practices and the potential for biogas uptake. The study was part of the Horizon 2020-funded project "Science Transformation in Europe through Citizen's Involvement in Health, Conservation and Energy Research" (Step Change). The project launched a citizen science collaborative project in Uganda which gathered responses from 1,068 farming households through individual interviews. In addition, 48 farmers were engaged in six focus group discussions (FGDs), as well 20 key informant interviews targeting government ministries and departments, the private sector, and non-government organisations involved in the promotion of biogas technology. Case stories of successful adoption of biogas technology at the farm level were gathered from other parts of the county.

Participants were predominantly farmers practicing subsistence and commercial agriculture. In general legumes and cereals were mostly grown on a subsistence scale while cash crops such as coffee, cotton, tobacco, and vanilla were grown on a commercial basis. Kyankwanzi district mainly grows cereals for subsistence and commercial farming compared to other crops. Luwero and Kiboga districts produced slightly more fruits and legumes respectively. Luwero district had a higher number of members growing cash crops, compared to other districts. At least 100% of the households own some form of livestock, both at commercial and subsistence levels.

In the three districts, poultry was the major livestock reared mainly on subsistence farming with Kiboga district having the highest number of poultry farmers. Fish farming was scanty in the three districts with Luwero having none. Kiboga district had many cattle and goats rearing for commercial and subsistence farming respectively. More farmers in Luwero reared pigs mainly for commercial purposes. Irrespective of the scale of operation, the production of crops and rearing of animals provide biomass which is a potential feedstock for gasification plants and biogas production.

² Citizen science is scientific research conducted with participation from the general public.

Adoption of biogas technology

Results of the Citizen Science study showed a very low adoption rate for biogas in the study districts; 3.1% compared to solar technology at a 77% adoption rate. Respondents mentioned some barriers to adoption that include lack of funds to afford the initial cost of installing the technology, scarcity of information in rural areas on renewable energy opportunities, inaccessibility of technical personnel, limited knowledge of maintenance procedures, high maintenance costs, theft, and material shortages. This is corroborated by (Mukisa et al., 2022) who report inadequate access to knowledge, lack of investment capital, and technical expertise to sustain the technology as the key bottlenecks for widespread development of biogas technology in Uganda.

Experiences gained from NGOs promoting biogas show that investment in biogas technology requires some investment in cattle farming for the constant supply of raw materials to reduce reliance on biomass only. A modest package of a biogas system with one Friesian crossbreed cow costs approximately UGX 6,000,000/= (Euro 1,428.6), besides the cost of constructing a shed for the animal. This cost is prohibitive to smallholders.

Despite the current low adoption rate, citizen scientists indicated awareness of the benefits of biogas. This awareness can be harnessed through more training and financial support to ensure wide-scale adoption. The mentioned benefits include access to clean energy for cooking, saving on firewood costs, and increased crop production from the use of slurry while saving the cost of fertilisers.

Ms Tumwebaze Faith, a current user of biogas in Mityana Municipality shared an experience of the benefits of the biogas technology. Biogas was introduced to her farm in 2011 with support from Heifer International and she currently utilises it for cooking, lighting, and production of slurry. The immediate benefits from biogas as reported by Faith include increased banana production from an average of 90-100 bunches a season to over 160 bunches.

The increased yields are attributed to the use of slurry. Also, the farmer mentioned that she adds at least 18kg of dried slurry residue to pig feed, saving her at least UGX 20,000 (Euro 4.8) per 100kg bag of complete pig feed. Investment in biogas therefore remains a worthwhile investment to address multiple benefits at farm level as well as achieving sustainable energy access.

Banana plantation fertilised with bioslurry. Photo credit: ARUWE

Barriers to biogas deployment

The production potential of domestic biogas has not been fully exploited due to lingering policy, institutional and technical constraints. Based on literature and citizen science study, the key challenges include:

- i. The lack of appropriate technical skills at the local levels for the installation and operation of biogas,
- ii. The absence of scalable models for domestic and commercial-scale biogas energy production,
- iii. Limited awareness about opportunities for biogas applications and their economic viability,
- iv. The initial cost of installation is high and relatively unaffordable by smallholders,
- v. Inadequate and intermittent government support, and
- vi. Behavioural and social acceptance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Technical support

The Government and stakeholders need to render technical support through training to improve the acceptability and usability of the technology. This may include training programmes for technicians, installers, and maintenance personnel.

Awareness

All Actors conduct outreach programmes to educate rural communities about the benefits of biogas, including reduced fuel costs, improved indoor air quality, and waste management. Through social marketing campaigns create demand for biogas technology and promote its advantages among rural communities.

Financial Mechanisms

Government and implementing organisations provide financial incentives, subsidies, or low-interest loans to make biogas systems more affordable for rural households. These can be through community-led village savings and loan associations, government subsidies, guarantee schemes, or tailored bank loans.

Technology development

Government and development partners should consider strategies that could reduce the technology cost, e.g., manufacturing low-cost balloon digesters locally instead of importing prefabricated digesters. Invest in research to develop more efficient, affordable, and user-friendly biogas technologies that cater to rural needs.

Community-based approaches

Civil society organisations should encourage community initiatives and cooperatives for shared biogas systems, spreading the costs and benefits across multiple households.

Government policy support

Civil society organisations and development partners continue to advocate for policies that promote biogas adoption, including tax incentives and regulatory support.

Monitoring and evaluation

All actors implement monitoring and evaluation systems to assess the performance of biogas projects, use data to make informed decisions and improve future projects, and share success stories and lessons learned to inspire and guide other communities.

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Off-grid Renewable Energy in Agriculture: Promoting Charcoal Briquettes in Uganda

This Policy Brief reviews policy and practice in the use of charcoal briquettes in agriculture with a particular focus on their impact on rural farming communities in Uganda. The brief underscores the urgent need to promote charcoal briquettes as a viable and sustainable alternative to traditional charcoal biomass use in Uganda, thus mitigating deforestation while significantly improving indoor air quality. To harness these benefits, this brief proposes a multifaceted approach that includes public awareness campaigns, policy support, investment in research and development, capacity building for smallholders, and initiatives to expand the market for charcoal briquettes. By adopting these measures, Uganda can foster an environmentally responsible and economically viable charcoal briquette industry that not only conserves forests but also enhances the livelihoods of countless Ugandans, especially in rural areas, while reducing the health risks associated with traditional biomass use.

Cover photo: Nkandwa cooperative member display charcoal briquettes (Credit: ARUWE)

Globally, large volumes of waste are generated in different parts of the world following population growth, and as economies around the world expand. The World Bank estimates of global waste generation is that by 2050 waste generation will increase from 2.01 billion tonnes to about 3.40 billion tonnes (Edodi, 2023). According to the Africa Waste Management Outlook (Neale et al., 2021), current waste management practices in Africa are causing economic, social, and environmental impacts. The Global Waste Management Outlook report recommends a twofold priority action to tackle these impacts namely, bring waste under control and harness the opportunity of 'waste as a resource' by exploring wastes as a livelihood resource.

In Uganda, there is a considerable volume of waste generated by Uganda's farms especially bananas (4.3 tonnes annually) and pineapples (15,960 tons per season) (Mibulo et al., 2023). Coupled with the current shortage of energy sources in the country and environmental degradation problems resulting from deforestation in Uganda, there is a potential for sustainable utilization of such organic waste through the conversion into briquettes (Abondio et al., 2020; Mkude et al., 2021). Briquettes made from agricultural residues offset the wood harvesting thereby preventing deforestation. In addition, the briquettes are 20 to 30 percent cheaper than the regular charcoal in Uganda. They can be produced locally, and they generate less smoke than wood charcoal.

Charcoal briquettes are therefore an eco-friendly, energy-efficient, and low-technology fuel source that offers a cleaner alternative for household and agricultural use. The transition to such sustainable alternatives within Uganda's energy system is not only beneficial but also essential in the long-term effort to mitigate environmental degradation and reduce the impact of climate change while contributing to agriculture production (Kyayesimira & Florence, 2021).

Promoting Charcoal Briquettes

Over the past years, ARUWE has strategically implemented decentralized renewable energy systems, with a specific focus on promoting the use of charcoal briquettes, to uplift rural women farmers. These systems empower women by placing them at the forefront of energy production and distribution, fostering skills and ownership.

Charcoal briquettes, as a sustainable energy source, not only enhance accessibility but also create economic opportunities for women, who may be involved in the production and commercialization processes. This approach aligns with ARUWE's gender lens, ensuring that women actively participate in decision-making regarding the choice of technology and distribution of benefits. By addressing the unique needs of women in rural areas, particularly in terms of clean energy, ARUWE's initiatives contribute to economic empowerment, sustainable practices, and improved well-being for women farmers.

Additionally, ARUWE is intensifying efforts to implement integrated climate resilience approaches by refocusing on promoting RE technologies including charcoal briquettes, creating awareness to increase their application in various agricultural value chains.

Using the citizen approach, science, an emerging field that refers to the active engagement of the general public in scientific research, ARUWE undertook a study to gather evidence of the economic, environmental, and societal impacts of adopting charcoal briquettes in agricultural production in rural Uganda and explored the potential for scaling up this technology at the national level. Data were collected from 1068 respondents in 3 rural districts in Uganda – Kyankwanzi, Kiboga and Luwero. In addition, 48 respondents were involved in six focus group discussions. Case stories of the successful use of charcoal briquettes in agriculture were also captured. At the national level, 20 key informant interviews were conducted targeting government ministries and departments, the private sector, and non-government organisations involved in the promotion of charcoal briquettes. Case stories of the successful use of charcoal briquettes in agriculture were also captured.

Results from the study underscore the pivotal role of charcoal briquettes in Uganda's agricultural sector, revealing that 4.1% of participants actively utilise this renewable energy source. The use of briquettes enables sustainable production practices and income generation. Conversion of agricultural waste to make briquettes leads to sustainable waste management reducing pollution. Respondents further highlighted that the adoption of briquette production significantly reduces deforestation activities, mitigating soil erosion and land degradation. Consequently, this adoption acts as a crucial measure in averting drought and enhancing the protection of the natural environment, ultimately bolstering crop productivity.

“Making and using briquettes has reduced deforestation, the main causes of desertification and soil erosion. Therefore, the adoption of production and use of briquettes averts drought and increases protection of the natural environment, thus increasing the productivity of crops.” Nkandwa cooperative focus group discussion.

Beyond energy production, farmers crafting and selling briquettes illustrated the economic potential and versatility of this eco-friendly alternative in rural and urban communities. Respondents also mentioned that briquette production provides an alternative source of income. Respondents also mentioned the empowerment of women and children as a direct social benefit of using charcoal briquettes. Women have both reproductive and productive burdens. The productive burden of looking for and using firewood is reduced as they use briquettes since such fuels are quicker and do not require their presence during the cooking process. The saved time is utilized in agricultural activities.

“When I cook using briquettes, I don't have to stay in the kitchen to regulate the fire. So, I put the day's food on the energy-saving stove and go weed my crops or feed the chicken.” Mrs Mukakakere Regina.

Briquettes have been used in agricultural production activities such as poultry farming (in young chicken brooders) cutting on expenditure and minimizing carbon emissions from charcoal and other biomass. Nannyanzi Hawa Kevin, a farmer in Nakaseke operates a poultry farm rearing kroiler and indigenous chickens. She uses briquettes to warm young chicks in their brooder. She makes briquettes using biochar, water, tiny stones, and cassava starch.

“I saw that the briquettes are less costly and time-effective compared to charcoal in poultry farming. A bag of charcoal costs UGX 60,000/= (Euro 14.3) and it lasted only a month. When I started using briquettes mixed with charcoal, I saved 50% of what I was initially spending on charcoal. With briquettes, one can use the available resources to mold them.” Says Kevin

Chicks in a brooder as Savio Mak-kristo's farm using briquettes (photo credit: ARUWE)

Challenges to the adoption of charcoal briquettes in Uganda

The adoption of charcoal briquettes in Uganda faces several challenges, including:

- Lack of awareness - many Ugandans are unaware of the benefits of charcoal briquettes and how they compare to traditional charcoal or firewood. Additionally, inadequate consumer awareness and education result in improper handling of briquettes discouraging first-time users.
- High initial costs - the cost of purchasing or setting up equipment for charcoal briquette production can be a barrier for individuals or small businesses.
- Inconsistent government policies - the regulatory environment for charcoal briquette production and use is inconsistent, leading to uncertainty for producers and consumers.
- Infrastructure for waste collection - in areas where organic waste is used as a feedstock for briquette production, the lack of proper waste collection and management systems can be a challenge.
- Lack of skills and training - a lack of training and skills for briquette production and usage can be a barrier. Investing in training and capacity-building is crucial.
- Lack of local manufacturing capacity - the country relies on imported equipment, making production expensive and limiting availability of charcoal briquettes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Public-private partnerships

There is a need to foster a robust collaboration among government, agricultural organizations, non-governmental entities, and private sectors to facilitate the distribution and marketing of briquettes.

Financial Incentives and Subsidies

The Government needs to provide financial incentives, such as tax breaks or subsidies, to reduce the cost of setting up briquette production units and to make briquettes more affordable for consumers.

Quality Standards and Certification

The Government needs to establish and enforce quality standards for charcoal briquettes used in agriculture to ensure that they meet specific nutrient content and safety criteria. Certification programs can help build trust among consumers by ensuring consistency and quality.

Market Development and Distribution Support

The Government and civil society organisations need to develop and support distribution networks for briquettes, particularly in rural and underserved areas. There is a need to encourage private sector involvement to expand market reach for the technology.

Research and extension services

The Government and civil society organisations should invest in research and extension services to educate farmers on the benefits of using charcoal briquettes in agriculture. This should include provision of training and information on application methods and best practices. Research and innovation into this technology can be encouraged by offering grants or incentives to institutions and businesses working on improving briquette technology and production.

Environmental Regulations

The Government should implement and enforce environmental regulations that promote sustainable and responsible sourcing of biomass for briquette production. This includes reforestation initiatives and sustainable biomass management. Integrate the promotion of briquettes into national energy and environmental policies, emphasizing their role in reducing deforestation and improving air quality.

Public Awareness Campaigns

All actors need to launch extensive public awareness campaigns to educate consumers about the benefits of briquettes, both in terms of cost savings and environmental impact such as reduced deforestation and improved soil health.

Training and Capacity Building for Local Production

All actors need to encourage the local production of charcoal briquettes by providing training and access to equipment for small-scale producers. This can stimulate job creation in rural areas.

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